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Internet advertising and its popularity

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1. Introduction

Due to the rapid expansion of the Internet, online advertising has evolved into one of the essential advertising mediums. The Internet is a virtual environment where customers connect with many advertisements. Advertisers may use the Internet to maintain and improve relationships with customers worldwide, representing a great new approach for businesses to engage with new and existing audiences in a very integrated way. The one-to-many or many-to-many paradigm of online advertising can be used. Online advertising has the advantage of being interactive when compared to traditional advertising. Consumers are no longer passive recipients of advertising when they use this medium; instead, they become collaborators with the marketer. If people are interested in online advertising, they will attentively read the advertisement, click on it, go to the advertiser's website to learn more about the goods, and maybe place an order online. As a result, internet advertising is more accurately described as rational and compelling advertising.

Digital advertising has evolved into one of the most important marketing platforms in the world. Global digital advertising revenue is expected to hit an all-time high of 366 billion dollars in 2021, thanks to increased internet penetration rates and rising demand for online content, particularly during the pandemic. This amount is even more astonishing when you realize that it represents roughly two-thirds of all worldwide advertising spending. Even though this innovative and dynamic type of advertising has seen a significant increase in popularity in many areas of the world, the digital advertising sector is getting more centralized and competitive every year.

Google continues to lead the list of online corporations with the most digital advertising income globally. In 2026, the search engine behemoth is expected to produce \$357 billion in sales, accounting for nearly 44% of worldwide digital ad revenues. By 2026, Facebook's advertising-income is predicted to reach approximately 203 billion US dollars. These two firms and other important participants in the digital advertising market, such as Amazon, Apple, TikTok, and Twitter, are referred to as "walled gardens." The fact that these platforms are closed ecosystems in

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which the publisher controls all (advertising) operations without sharing the information with third parties distinguishes them from the open Internet.

Marketers may pick from a wide range of digital advertising channels, which are constantly developing. According to the most recent data, search advertising remains one of the most popular digital ad formats worldwide, which is unsurprising given that search engines produce around 30% of global online traffic each year. Mobile advertising is another popular kind of digital promotion, as millions of people use their smartphones and tablets to access the Internet regularly. In 2021, global mobile advertising spending will approach 288 billion dollars, with mobile marketing activities accounting about 88% of total internet ad spending in countries like China and Mexico. Meanwhile, because of remarkable user counts and engagement rates on platforms like Instagram and TikTok, social media has evolved into one of the most important drivers of (mobile) advertising development. In 2022, spending on social media advertising is predicted to top 130 billion dollars; by 2028, it will have nearly doubled.

2. Advantages of the Internet Advertising

Target marketing—one of the most appealing aspects of online advertising is targeting certain groups of people with minimal waste. Advertisements on the Internet may be tailored to particular clients based on age, gender, income, education, hobbies, interests, and geographic area.

Message tailoring—Because of precision targeting, communications may be tailored to appeal to the target audience's unique requirements and desires. Because of the Internet's interactive features, one-to-one marketing can be done more successfully in both the commercial and consumer sectors.

Interactive capabilities- because the Internet is interactive, it provides strong potential for increasing customer involvement and satisfaction and almost immediate feedback for buyers and sellers.

Information access—perhaps the most significant benefit of internet advertising is its availability as a source of uninterrupted continuous information 24x7. Internet users may access a wealth of knowledge on practically any subject by clicking on the ad. They may acquire a lot of data on product characteristics, pricing, and purchasing information, among other things. If requested, links will take readers to even more information.

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Enhancing customer engagement - is a goal for marketers that want to communicate successfully with their consumers and improve their brand experience. This is made feasible via interactive online advertisements.

Potential for sales- Internet advertising aims to increase sales via the brand's website and partner networks. This medium's sales potential has been rising over time. Conversion and branding goals might be pursued simultaneously in such initiatives.

Creativity—creatively produced online commercials may improve a company's image and favorably position it in the minds of consumers.

Exposure- The World Wide Web allows many smaller businesses with limited expenditures to acquire exposure to potential clients that would otherwise be unattainable. Companies may acquire national and even worldwide exposure quickly for a fraction of the cost that would be necessary via traditional media.

Stressing brand message- Many marketers combine a traditional ad campaign with a digital one to raise the chances that their message will resonate with their target demographic and enhance their brand image.

Complements IMC- The Internet complements other IMC media complement and. As a result, it's an important link in the integrative process.

3. Disadvantages of the Internet Advertising

Measurement Problem— one of the most significant drawbacks of the Internet is the lack of trustworthiness of the research figures created. A brief examination of projections, audience profiles, and other figures provided by research firms reveals a tremendous level of variation, indicating a major lack of validity and trustworthiness.

Websnarl- It might take a long time to obtain information from Internet advertisements. When many people visit a site, the time it takes to load rises, and certain sites may become unreachable owing to the high volume of visitors. This is a huge drawback for many consumers who demand fast. Broadband is assisting in the reduction of this issue.

Clutter- As the quantity of adverts increases, the chances of one's ad getting spotted decreases. Consequently, some advertisements may go unnoticed, and some customers may become annoyed by the clutter.

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Potential for deception- In response to advertisers' attempts to target youngsters with subtle advertising messages, the Centre for Media Education has referred to the Internet as "a web of deception." Data harvesting without users' knowledge or consent, hackers, and credit card fraud are just a few of the issues that the Internet faces.

Privacy- Internet marketers, like their direct marketing colleagues, must be cautious not to intrude on customers' privacy.

Limited production quality- Although it is developing, internet advertising still lacks the production skills of many competing mediums. While improved technology and rich media are helping to close the gap, the Internet still trails certain conventional media in this area.

Poor reach- While the Internet is expanding at a breakneck pace, its reach still lags far behind that of television. The majority of Indians are computer illiterate and do not have access to the Internet. As a result, the media is unable to reach the people.

Irritation- Numerous research has documented the vexing characteristics of some online strategies. According to these researchers, consumers are dissatisfied with clutter, e-mail spam, and pop-ups and pop-unders. Visitors will be deterred from visiting websites and seeing online advertisements due to these vexing features.

Overall, the Internet has several distinct benefits from traditional media for marketers. However, the shortcomings and limits of this medium make it less than a one-stop-shop. On the other hand, the Internet is a highly helpful instrument in marketing communications.

4. Types of the Internet Advertising

The main advantage of online advertising is that it allows for the rapid publication of content without any geographic boundary or time. Advertisers may personalize their ads on the Internet, making consumer targeting more efficient and accurate. For example, adWords, Yahoo! Search, and Google AdSense allow adverts to be displayed on relevant websites or alongside related search results. On the other hand, consumers have more influence over the material they view, influencing the time, placement, and prominence of internet ads. Display advertising, mobile advertising, affiliate marketing, search engine optimization, and social networks are examples of online advertising in Internet marketing.

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Ad formats have evolved, reflecting the fierce battle for audience attention in a consumer-driven economy. Still, the following are some of the most prevalent forms utilized by internet advertisers:

Display ads: Graphics, whitespace, and text are used unusually in commercials. These advertisements are a variation of classic banners and are available in various sizes. Rectangles, pop-ups, banners, buttons, and skyscraper display advertisements all take up different amounts of pixel space on websites that can be rented. Advertisers frequently utilize these advertisements since they aid in brand awareness when viewed by site visitors. Furthermore, highly targeted display advertising, such as a local Facebook ad shown solely to persons with profiles that fit the target market description, may create significant click-through rates.

Rich media ads: All commercials in this category are interactive since they give customers a click-through option. The customer proceeds to the advertiser's website after clicking on the ad, where the transaction or other goal is completed. According to Wikipedia writers, rich media advertising frequently incorporates Flash animation and various other aspects to grab attention. Rich media can be any of the following formats:

Banner ad is a visual picture or animation used to promote a product or service on a website, in an application, or an HTML e-mail. This type of internet advertising predates even search engines. In this situation, marketers place a banner on a related website (typically with a captivating image and headline). Users that click the banners will be sent to the marketer's website, where they may potentially make a purchase. The difficulty is that online users have acquired "banner blindness," which means that only a small fraction of individuals click on the advertisement.

Interstitial ad - A page of advertisements is displayed before the desired material.

A floating ad floats above the content or travels across the user's screen.

Expanding ad is an ad that changes size and can potentially modify the content of a webpage.

Polite ad is a technique for downloading a massive ad in tiny chunks so that the information being seen is not disrupted.

Wallpaper ad is an advertisement that alters the appearance of the page being viewed.

Trick banner- a banner ad in the shape of a dialogue window with buttons

Pop-up- a new window that pops up in front of the existing one to show an advertising or the complete webpage

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Pop-under- Another window is loaded behind the current window, similar to a pop-up, which is not visible to the user until active windows are closed.

Video ad Instead of a static or dynamic picture, simple moving video snippets are presented, similar to a banner ad.

Video game ad- advertisements that occur in online games.

Contextual ads: Ad servers, such as Facebook's or Google's DoubleClick, keep track of client advertising and show them to relevant users as they visit specific pages on websites. If a person looks for fashion garments on an electronic retail site that uses double click, the adverts for fashion garments may appear on the user's e-mail page. This is referred to as providing particular ad targeting based on profile data. This is beneficial to marketers in terms of micro-segmentation, and it is beneficial to users in terms of receiving relevant adverts at the precise moment they want information. This is also the foundation for Google's Ad Sense program, which allows online advertisers to bid for keywords and display their advertisements on Google search engine result pages or websites that allow them. As a result, contextual adverts, the most common type of internet advertising, are included in the keyword search category.

E-mail advertising- is one of the most cost-effective forms of web marketing. It's simply a few words of text tucked within the company's website. Advertisers pay for space in an e-mail that is sponsored by someone else. They like to send them e-mail newsletters alerting them about the goods. This makes it much easier to reach an audience who wants to receive an e-mail that contains information about their website's content. It is one of the oldest methods still in use today.

Sponsorships - often known as advertorials are a type of sponsorship. They make an effort to combine editorial material with promotional messages. Advertisers like this approach because it gives them more visibility and the idea that the magazine supports their product. Sponsorships are crucial on the web since people tend to ignore display adverts, and sponsorships allow for a lot of interaction because many companies form synergistic relationships to create relevant content.

Mobile advertising—as we all know, smartphones and mobile phones are becoming increasingly popular. The number of people using the Internet on their phones is increasing daily. People are increasingly using their mobile devices to access the Internet. Advertisers may take advantage of

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this popular medium by using numerous formats available for mobile advertising, such as banner display advertisements, short messaging service (SMS), video ads, voice commercials, and so on.

Social network advertising - is a type of internet advertising that may be seen on sites like Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. Direct display adverts put on social networks can be used to advertise on such networks. Facebook and Instagram have benefits in that they employ an easy-to-use advertising system that covers many topics. This helps advertisers avoid wasting money on those who aren't interested in what their website has to offer by narrowing down the exact target demographic who will be interested in adverts. The advertising will only be seen to Facebook and Instagram users who fall inside the specified demographic.

Affiliate marketing is a terrific type of internet promotion for physical things or digital information products like e-books and other courses. Marketers form partnerships with other websites to advertise their products in this situation. The main benefit is that they don't have to pay a commission to their affiliates until the deal is completed. If marketers successfully promote their affiliate program in the right areas, their affiliates may take care of most of the job for them, such as employing pay-per-click advertising and eventually sending traffic to their product in various ways.

Pay-per-click (PPC) advertising - is a relatively new type of online advertising. When a user puts a certain word into a search engine, a relevant text ad with a link to a corporate website appears. A series of text advertisements, commonly labeled as 'sponsored links,' is presented on the right-hand side of search engine pages. Unlike traditional advertising, advertisers do not pay when their advertisements are shown; instead, they pay when their ads are clicked, resulting in a visit to the advertiser's website—hence the name "pay per click." Although some attrition may not be controlled, most clicks result in a visit to the site. Marketers must be aware of this. Pay-per-click advertising is a great option for businesses with the financial capabilities and willingness to invest in bringing targeted traffic to their websites. Google AdWords traffic is deemed targeted, just like SEO traffic, because individuals are typing in keyword phrases related to the items and services they are looking for before clicking on their ad. This may instantly deliver a flood of visitors to an internet firm, and it's a great option if marketers can turn it into profit.

5. Conclusion

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Finally, there are several benefits and drawbacks to advertising on the Internet. The benefits of online advertising outweigh the negatives in my perspective. Having an internet advertisement, which allows the advertisement to be seen worldwide, takes business to a whole new level, allowing it to reach a much larger audience. Its low cost allows small businesses to invest in internet marketing while lowering their initial marketing costs. The Internet's enormous breadth also allows everyday people to encounter more commercial offerings and makes it a handy shopping destination. Other traditional purchasing techniques, such as traveling to a store to pay payments, allow consumers to obtain more time out of their lives. The Internet has benefited humans in a variety of ways. There will always be problems, but the positives, in my opinion, exceed the cons. The World Wide Web is always evolving; in this case, it would offer a better environment for online advertising. It is the most effective advertising approach compared to all other media and consistently produces results.

6. Bibliography

- Berthon, P., Pitt, L. F., & Watson, R. T. (1996). The World Wide Web as an advertising medium: Toward an understanding of conversion efficiency. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 36(1), 43-54.
- Bhatnagar, A., & Papatla, P. (2001). Identifying locations for targeted advertising on the Internet. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 5(3), 23-45.
- Blattberg, R. C., & Deighton, J. (1991). Interactive marketing: Exploiting the age of addressability. *Sloan Management Review*, 32(1), 5-14.
- Broussard, G. (2000). How advertising frequency can work to build online advertising effectiveness. *International Journal of Market Research*, 42(4), 439-458.
- Bush, A. J., Bush, V., & Harris, S. (1998). Advertiser perceptions of the Internet as a marketing communications tool. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 38(2), 17-27.
- Dahlen, M., Rasch, A., & Rosengren, S. (2003). Love at first site? A study of Website advertising effectiveness. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 43(1), 25-33.
- Paul, P. (1996). Marketing on the Internet. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 13(4), 2-39.
- Peppers, D., & Rogers, M. (1993). *The one to one future: Building relationships one customer at a time*. New York: Currency Doubleday.